

Bee fauna in coastal sand dunes of Ariakehama and ten islands along the Seto Inland Sea, Western Japan

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Abstract

The bee fauna in coastal sand dunes of Ariakehama (mainland of Shikoku Island) and ten islands along the Seto Inland Sea, western Japan were investigated. In Ariakehama, bees were quantitatively collected from April to October in 2008, and the summer bee fauna on the coastal shrub, *Vitex rotundifolia*, was surveyed in ten islands between 2003 to 2021. In Ariakehama, the bee diversity was only 20 species, like in some other study sites of coastal sand dunes in Japan. *Megachile kobensis* and *Apis mellifera* were the dominant species. Compared to other coastal sand dunes in Japan, remarkable characteristics of the bee fauna in Ariakehama were the scarcity of *Hylaeus* spp. and *Lasioglossum frigidum*. These bees were common in some islands in the Seto Inland Sea. The reasons for their rarity in Ariakehama were discussed.

Key words: bee diversity, pollination, sand dune.

Introduction

Physical environment of coastal sand dunes is generally harsh for the majority of terrestrial animals and plants, due to high salt concentration, strong winds, shifting sands and other stressors (Maun, 2009). Thus, the flora and fauna in coastal sand dunes are unique, including specialists found only in such a habitat. In Europe, coastal sand dunes are well known for hosting several endangered arthropods, especially bees and wasps (Howe et al. 2010). Unique bee fauna in coastal dunes is also known in the New World (e.g., Cane et al. 1996; Viana & Kleinert, 2015; Abbate et al. 2019). In Japan, novel bee fauna on sandy coasts was firstly revealed by Hiasa *et al.* (1993), based on the research of summer bee fauna in Yumigahama, Tottori prefecture: all the dominant species were specialists found only in coastal dunes. After that, the coastal bee fauna has been quantitatively investigated throughout the year in some areas facing the Sea of Japan and the Pacific (Fig. 1) (Minagi et al. 2001; Negoro, 2001; Gōukon, 2006; Inoue & Endo, 2006; Hisamatsu, 2011). The coastal sand dune is one of the most endangered habitats in Japan (Yura, 2014). Therefore, floral, and faunal studies are urgent to establish conservation strategies.

After the wild bee survey on the campus of Hokkaido University in 1959 (Sakagami & Fukuda, 1973), quantitative investigations of the bee fauna have been carried out in several places in Japan. However, the bee fauna has so far been investigated in neither coastal nor inland areas around the Seto Inland Sea. Environmental conditions of coastal sand dunes facing the inland sea may be different from those facing the Sea of Japan and the Pacific Ocean. For example, the wave height of an inland sea is generally negligible if compared to an open sea. Furthermore, in western Japan, precipitation around the Seto Inland Sea is lower (ca 1000–1300 mm/year) than that in sites facing the Pacific Ocean (e.g. 2500 mm/year in Kochi city) and the Sea of Japan (e.g. 1900 mm/year in Tottori city) (Fig. 1). These environmental conditions may affect the coastal bee fauna.

In this manuscript, the bee fauna in coastal sand dunes in the Seto Inland Sea is reported. Firstly, the bee fauna was periodically investigated in 2008 in Ariakehama, mainland of Kagawa Prefecture, according to the standard protocol of faunal survey of bees (Sakagami & Fukuda, 1973). Then, the summer bee fauna on the coastal shrub *Vitex rotundifolia* L.f. (Lamiaceae)—which harbors the richest in both species' diversity and abundance of bees in coastal sand dunes in western Japan— was investigated in ten islands in the Seto Inland Sea (Fig 1) from 2003 to 2021. Recently, Koyama and Ide (2020) showed that in the coastal sand dunes of the Kanto region, Honshu, bee diversity is lower in areas without a back-dune than those with one. In Ariakehama, the tide embankment is constructed behind the sand dune vegetation along most of the coast, and the area with back-dune is limited, just for c.a. 400 m length along the coastline. To know the effects of back-dune on the bee fauna, bees visiting *Vitex rotundifolia* were investigated in areas with and without back-dune in August 2019. A part of distributional records of some rare bees has already been reported in local journals of entomology (Ito 2008, 2012, 2014, 2016).

Materials and methods

Periodical survey in Ariakehama in 2008. The periodical sampling was made at the sand dune of Ariakehama (34.1385°N, 133.6412°E), Kan-onji-shi, Kagawa-ken, Shikoku Island, western Japan in 2008 (Fig. 1). Monthly changes in average precipitation and average temperature are shown in (Fig. 2).

In the sand dune, typical coastal vegetation is distributed c.a. 2.0 km along the coastline. A tide embankment (c.a. 2 to 3 m height) is constructed behind the coastal vegetation for c.a. 1.5 km. Behind the

As shown in the results, bees were the most abundant on the flowers of a coastal shrub *Vitex rotundifolia*. Coastal bee fauna visiting *V. rotundifolia* was investigated on ten islands in the Seto Inland Sea (Fig. 1). On each island, coastal bees visiting *V. rotundifolia* were collected for two to five hours from mid-July to early September, between 2003 to 2021.

Comparison of bee fauna between areas with and without back-dune.

On 9 August 2019, three small sites were chosen in each of the areas with and without back dune in Ariakehama. At each site, bees visiting *Vitex rotundifolia* were recorded for 20 min (60 min in each area).

Identification of bees.

Bees collected in this survey were identified by the author according to Kikuchi et al. (2004) and Tadauchi and Murao (2014) or comparing specimens that were identified by Dr. M. Goubara. Some specimens were identified by Dr. R. Murao.

Results

Bee fauna in Ariakehama

A total of 232 bees belonging to 20 species in 14 genera of five families were collected throughout the periodical survey in 2008 (Table 1). Among the five families, Megachilidae, for which 114 individuals of nine species were collected, was the most dominant family in Ariakehama. Only two dominant species had a lower 95% confidence limit of relative abundance exceeding the average percentage ($5.3\% = 100 \times 1/S$, where S is the total number of species): *Megachile kobensis* Cockerell, 1918 (77 individuals) and *Apis mellifera* L., 1758 (65 individuals) (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Relative abundance (bar) and cumulative frequency (black circle) of bees collected in Ariakehama. Average percentage and 95% confidence limit were calculated according to Sakuma

(1964).95% confidence limit of average percentage = $\left(\frac{n}{N} \pm 2\sqrt{n(N-n)/N^3}\right) \times 100$, where N is total number of individuals, n is the number of individuals of a given species.

Table 1. Bee fauna in Ariakehama, Kan-onji-shi, Kagawa Prefecture, collected in 2008. All females of *A. mellifera* and *B. ignitus* are workers. H: Highly dependent on coastal dune, S: Slightly dependent on coastal dune, I: Inland species.

	Category	No. individuals		
		♂	♀	Total
Colletidae				
<i>Hylaeus matsumurai</i> Bridwell, 1919	S	1	0	1
Andrenidae				
<i>Andrena knuthi</i> Alfken, 1990	I	0	1	1
Halictidae				
<i>Lasioglossum frigidum</i> Sakagami et Ebmer, 1996	H	3	11	14
Megachilidae				
<i>Anthidium septemspinosum</i> Lepeletier, 1841	I	2	1	3
<i>Coelioxys formosicola</i> Strand, 1913	H	4	6	10
<i>Coelioxys sakamotorum</i> Nagase, 2006	I	0	1	1
<i>Megachile disjunctiformis</i> Cockerell, 1911	S	0	4	4
<i>Megachile kobensis</i> Cockerell, 1918	H	43	34	77
<i>Megachile nipponica</i> Cockerell, 1914	I	4	3	7
<i>Megachile sculpturalis</i> Smith, 1853	I	1	0	1
<i>Megachile subalbata</i> Yasumatsu, 1936	I	2	1	3
<i>Megachile tsurugensis</i> Cockerell, 1924	I	8	0	8
Apidae				
<i>Amegilla quadrifasciata</i> (Villers, 1789)	S	1	2	3
<i>Anthophora plumipes</i> (Pallas, 1772)	I	2	11	13
<i>Apis mellifera</i> Linnaeus, 1758	I	0	65	65
<i>Bombus ignitus</i> Smith, 1869	I	0	1	1
<i>Ceratina satoi</i> Yasumatsu, 1936	I	2	0	2
<i>Eucera spurcatipes</i> Pérez, 1905	S	9	0	9
<i>Thyreus centrimacula</i> (Pérez, 1905)	S	1	0	1
<i>Xylocopa appendiculata</i> Smith, 1852	I	1	7	8
		84	148	232

More than half of the bees collected in Ariakehama belonged to these two species. In addition, three other species were relatively dominant with more than 10 individuals collected: *Lasioglossum frigidum* Sakagami et Ebmer, 1996 (14 individuals), *Anthophora plumipes* (Pallas, 1772) (13 individuals), and *Celioxys formosicola* Strand, 1913 (10 individuals). Among the 20 species of bees, “highly dependent species” were *M. kobensis*, *C. formosicola* that is kleptoparasite of *M. kobensis*, and *L. frigidum*, and “slightly dependent species” were *Hylaeus matsumurai* Bridwell 1919, *Ceratina satoi* Yasumatsu 1936, *Amegilla quadrifasciata* (Villers, 1789), *Eucera spurcatipes* Pérez, 1905 and *Thyreus centrimacula* (Pérez,

1905). The remaining 12 species are commonly found in inland areas. Thus, 119 of 232 bees collected in this periodical survey are dependent to some degree on the coastal dune.

Bees were the most abundant and species-rich in *Vitex rotundifolia* which was blooming from mid-June to mid-October. In total 102 individuals of 12 species including six coastal dependent species (82 bees) were collected from *V. rotundifolia* (Table 2). The second most bee-abundant flower was *Glehnia littoralis*, with 31 bees were observed. On *G. littoralis*, all bees except one were *A. mellifera*; the remaining individual was *Bombus ignitus* Smith. On *Potenilla chinensis* flowers, 14 individuals of four species were collected. Of which, three species (12 individuals) were coastal species. Flowers of *Heliotropium japonicum* were visited by only *A. mellifera*. *Raphanus sativus* var. *raphanistroides* flowers were visited by a few honeybees and one female of *Anthophora plumipes*. Only one individual bee (*L. frigidum*) was collected on flowers of *Dianthus japonica*. Thus, on this coast, *V. rotundifolia* and *Potenilla chinensis* were important flowers for coastal bees.

Table 2. Number of bees collected on six major coastal plants in Ariakehama. *worker. *Vr*, *Vitex rotundifolia*; *Gl*, *Glehnia littoralis*; *Pc*, *Potenilla chinensis*; *Hj*, *Heliotropium japonicum*; *Rs*, *Raphanus sativus* var. *hortensis* f. *raphanistroides*; *Dj*, *Dianthus japonicas*.

	<i>Vr</i>	<i>Gl</i>	<i>Pc</i>	<i>Hj</i>	<i>Rs</i>	<i>Dj</i>
Halictidae						
<i>Lasioglossum frigidum</i>	6♀		3♂1♀			1♀
Megachilidae						
<i>Anthidium septemspinosum</i>	2♂1♀					
<i>Coelioxys formosicola</i>	1♂5♀		2♂			
<i>Coelioxys sakamotoorum</i>	1♀					
<i>Megachile disjunctiformis</i>	4♀					
<i>Megachile kobensis</i>	38♂27♀		1♂2♀			
<i>Megachile nipponica</i>	2♂2♀					
<i>Megachile tsurugensis</i>	8♂					
Apidae						
<i>Amegilla quadrifasciata</i>	1♂					
<i>Anthophora plumipes</i>					1♀	
<i>Apis mellifera</i>	1♀*	30♀*		12♀*	4♀*	
<i>Bombus ignitus</i>		1♀*				
<i>Ceratina satoi</i>			2♂			
<i>Thyreus centrimacula</i>	1♂					
<i>Xylocopa appendiculata</i>	1♂1♀					
Total no. species	12	2	4	1	2	1
Total no. bees	102	31	11	12	5	1

Summer coastal bee fauna in ten islands.

On each island, two to six species of coastal bees were collected on *Vitex rotundifolia* (Table 3). As in Ariakehama, *M. kobensis* was dominant in all islands but Ogijima. Unlike Ariakehama, *Hylaeus* spp. were common in some islands. *Megachile xanthothrix* Yasumatsu et Hirashima, 1964 which is an endangered species in Japan and not found in Ariakehama, was abundant in two islands, Shiwaku-Teshima, and Awashima. The rare species *Thyreus centrimacula* was collected on four islands with its possible host species *Amegilla quadrifasciata*.

Bee fauna in areas with and without back-dune.

In total eight species were collected (Fig. 5), of which seven species were coastal species. The difference between the two areas was remarkable: only 18 individuals of two species were found in the area without back-dune whereas 44 individuals of 8 species were found in the area with back-dune.

H: Highly dependent on coastal dune, S: Slightly dependent on coastal sand dune. *Not collected. ** five females of *T. centrimacula* were collected on flowers of other unidentified plant near *Vites rotundifolia*.

Table 3. Summer coastal bees collected on *Vites rotundifolia* in Ariakehama and ten islands in Seto Inland Sea. The number of individuals of coastal bees collected was shown. Hours for collection were shown in parenthesis. Collection date of each study site was as follow. A: Ariakehama (July to September, 2008), b: Awashima (11 Aug., 4 Sept. 2015) c: Sanagijima (10 Sept. 2003, 24 Aug. 2011), d: Shiwaku Teshima (27 Aug. 2015), e: Naoshima (5 and 24 Aug. 2015), f: Teshima (Naoshima islands, 8 Aug. 2015), g: Ogijima (2 Aug., 12 Sept., 2015), h: Megijima (5 Sept 2015), i: Ôshima (31 July , 1 Aug. 2014), j: Shôdoshima (11 Aug. 2021), k: Miyajima (4 Aug. 2011).

Species	Category	A (18)	Islands									
			b(4)	c(5)	d(3)	e(5)	f(2)	g(2)	h(2)	i(2)	j(2)	k(2)
<i>Hylaeus macilentus</i>	H	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
<i>Hylaeus matsumurai</i>	S	1	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Hylaeus noomen</i>	H	0	6	1	0	0	0	10	4	0	1	0
<i>Lasioglossum frigidum</i>	H	7	0	0	7	6	1	2	0	6	0	3
<i>Megachile disjunctiformis</i>	S	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Megachile kobensis</i>	H	64	25	10	15	35	13	0	9	6	14	20
<i>Megachile xanthothrix</i>	S	0	5	0	7	0	0	1	0	0	1*	1
<i>Coelioxys formosicola</i>	H	6	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Amegilla quadrifasciata</i>	S	4	6	4	6	7	2	0	0	3	1	0
<i>Thyreus centrimacula</i>	S	1	0	0	1	0**	0	0	0	1	2	0
Total		87	42	18	37	48	16	13	13	16	19	25

Figure 5. Number of bees collected in areas with and without back dune. Number of individuals collected in each three sites was combined.

Discussion

The results of bee faunal surveys by the standard protocol in six coastal dunes in mainland Japan are summarized in Table 4. In addition to these six sites, Fukuda et al. (1973) reported bee fauna in and around the coastal dune of Hamakoshimizu, eastern Hokkaido, northern Japan. They collected 1045 individuals of 55 species. However, because many specimens were not identified to the species level, it remains unclear which are coastal species. Thus, their results are not considered in this paper. The number of bee species collected by the standard protocol in inland western Japan ranges from 31 (Nankoku-shi, Kochi Pref., Ikudome, 1978) to 87 species (Mt. Sanbe-san, Shimane Pref., Maeta et al. 2003). In contrast to these inland sites, species number is remarkably low in three of five coastal sand dunes so far reported, e.g. 16 (Gamou) to 22 (Hakoishi), while Ajigaura and Shimao harbor 48 and 47 species, respectively. The other characteristic is the exclusive dominance of a few coastal specialists. For example, 959 of 1092 bees (87%) in Gamou belong to seven species of coastal bees, of which *Hylaeus matsumurai* and *Lasioglossum frigidum* represent 75% of all bees. The percentage of coastal bees varies among study sites, ranging from 41% (Shimao) to 87% (Gamou). Species number obtained in Ariakehama is like that of Taisha, Hakoishi, and Gamou: only 19 species were collected (*A. mellifera* was omitted, because this species was usually neglected in research under the standard protocol), 78% of bees were coastal species, and one coastal specialist, *M. kobensis*, was particularly dominant, accounting for 49% of all bees. However, species composition in Ariakehama is different from other coastal sites (Fig. 6, Table 4): the most remarkable characteristic is the scarcity of *Hylaeus* spp. and *Lasioglossum frigidum*. Especially, *Hylaeus* was rare in Ariakehama: only one individual of *H. matsumurai* was collected in this research. In four of the five coastal sites, *Sphecodes amakusensis* Yasumatsu et Hirashima, 1951 a cleptoparasite of *L. frigidum*, was collected, but I never collected this species in Ariakehama. One of the reasons may be the low abundance of the host species.

Figure 6. NMDS plot illustrating bee community structure among six sandy coasts. Distance measure = Bray-Curtis. stress = 1e-04, silhouette=0.0604

The results of surveys in ten islands in the Seto Inland Sea suggest that *Hylaeus* spp. and *Lasioglossum frigidum* are not rare in this area. Thus, these bees can settle on sand dunes in the Seto Inland Sea, but some specific reasons in Ariakehama may explain the scarcity of these bees. One of the reasons may be the limitation of nest sites for *Hylaeus* spp. which usually nests inside dead plant stems (Almeida, 2008). In Taisha, the bamboo fences preventing sand movement are constructed along the sand dune, and these fences are nesting sites for *Hylaeus* spp. (Miyanaga R, pers. comm.). In contrast, in Ariakehama, such sites do not exist. On the other hand, the nesting habits of *L. frigidum* have not been reported to date. As most coastal species, *L. frigidum* was not collected in areas without a back-dune. In 2019, only one individual of *L. frigidum* was found in the area with a back-dune, while all individuals of *L. frigidum* collected in 2008 were found in areas with a back-dune, even though the details of collection sites were not recorded. In Kotogahama, a coastal sand dune in Kochi Prefecture, *L. frigidum* was also more abundant in areas with back-dune than in areas without back-dune (Ito, unpublished). *L. frigidum* may specifically nest in back-dune soil. I tried to find the nest sites of this species by chasing individuals foraged on flowers in Kotogahama, but I was unable to track these bees back to the nest because they fly away agilely. The nesting behavior of this species should be studied in future.

The present study reveals that the coastal bee fauna along the Seto Inland Sea includes species so far regarded as very rare and endangered bees, such as *Megachile xanthothrix*, *Amegilla quadrifasciata*, *Thyreus centrimacula* and *Anthidium septemspinatum* Lepeletier, 1841. *Thyreus centrimacula*, supposed to be a cleptoparasite of *Amegilla quadrifasciata*, is rare with only limited collection records (Sugiura & Gomi, 1991). This species seems to be widespread along the Seto Inland Sea, even though the density is low (Ito, 2014). *Megachile xanthothrix* is assigned as an endangered species by the Ministry of Environment in Japan, and even though it was not collected in Ariakehama, this species is very common in

Table 4. Comparison of coastal bee fauna among six study sites. *Apis mellifera* was excluded from results. Alphabets in parenthesis under locality name indicate the location in Fig. 1. 1 Minagi et al (2001), 2 Inoue and Endo (2006), 3 Negoro (2001), 4 Hisamatsu (2011), 5 Gōukon (2006).

Locality	Ariakehama (A)	Taisha ¹ (B)	Hakoishi ² (C)	Shimao ³ (D)	Ajigaura ⁴ (E)	Gamou ⁵ (F)
No. surveys	12	25	13	14	25	18
No. species	19	18	19	47	48	16
No. individuals	156	446	422*	1177	684	1092
No. individuals of coastal species (category)						
<i>Hylaeus macilentus</i> (H)	0	38	0	4	0	50
<i>Hylaeus matsumurai</i> (S)	1	0	0	15	0	151
<i>Hylaeus noomen</i> (H)	0	143	27	0	0	0
<i>Hylaeus pectoralis</i> (S)	0	0	0	0	0	45
<i>Lasioglossum frigidum</i> (H)	14	117	98	281	89	678
<i>Sphecodes amakusensis</i> (H)	0	4	0	6	2	10
<i>Megachile disjunctiformis</i> (S)	4	1	0	0	0	0
<i>Megachile kobensis</i> (H)	77	42	48	77	128	18
<i>Coelioxys formosicola</i> (H)	10	16	24	4	27	7
<i>Amegilla quadrifasciata</i> (S)	3	1	0	0	14	0
<i>Eucera spurcatipes</i> (S)	9	19	8	97	38	0
<i>Thyreus centrimacula</i> (S)	1	0	0	0	0	0
Total number of coastal bees	119	381	205	484	298	959
(% of all bees)	(78%)	(85%)	(49%)	(41%)	(44%)	(88%)

Shiwaku Teshima and Awashima islands (Ito, 2016). *Anthidium septemspinosum* was not collected in ten islands, but this species is also abundant in the other coast in Kagawa Prefecture (Ito, unpublished). *Coelioxys sakamotorum* Nagase, 2006 is firstly recorded from Shikoku Island. The abundance and species number of bees are generally rich in warm and xeric habitats (Michener, 2007). In this respect, around the Seto Inland Sea, where the average rainfall is ca. 1200 mm/year and sunny days are common, seems to be a suitable region for bees. Intensive studies of the bee fauna in this region will provide valuable insights into the faunal characteristics of bees in Japan.

Acknowledgements

I thank R. Murao and M. Gôbara for identification help, K. Gôukon and R. Miyanaga for useful comments during the course of research, reading the MS and comments on it, T. Endo for sending me a copy of their paper, Kagawa University for the financial support (grant for research that external funding is difficult to obtain), Y. Touyama for his help in bee collection in Miyajima Island, and J. Billen and A. Khalife for improving the English text and comments on the manuscript.

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